

The Impact of Team Work on Organizational Outcomes

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Abstract: In this study I have taken the most familiar private colleges in Oman-Muscat to apply my study on this kind of organization to identify the impact of teamwork of academic staff within the colleges they belong to and finding out the outcomes of organization due to the teamwork. This study was conducted by taking samples from each college in Sultanate of Oman –Muscat region. The colleges names are: Scientific College of Design, Mazoon College, Majan University College, Middle East College, Gulf College, German University of Technology in Oman, and Caledonian College of Engineering. The sample size was 95. And that focusing academic staff from each of these colleges from different departments. It is the descriptive research which have chosen the scale to measure the Impact of each Team Effectiveness on Organizational outcomes that has been conducted by questionnaire survey which include some factors of Team Effectiveness such as: team climate, interpersonal relationships, team communication, team composition and interact with wider organization. In other side also we can see that was four dependent variables such as the: Organizational commitment, organization learning, organization performance and organization development. The outcomes and finding of this research were measured by using the following methods such as: Checking the reliability of both Team Effectiveness and Organizational Outcomes, then we have shown the frequency according to the Demographic profile (Gender, Age group, Educational level, Department and Occupation), then we have check the correlation, the finding regarding the correlation was as follow: the correlation coefficient (Person) between Team Effectiveness and Organizational outcomes for members of the study sample of (.840) with significance level (0.00). This indicates that the Team Effectiveness and Perceived Organizational Outcomes is slightly significant because the significance value is reported as 0.000 which is nearly 0.05. After that we have checked the Regression result which we have got by using SPSS version 22, Based on the result it can be inferred that Team Effectiveness is significantly impacting Organizational outcomes because the variance explained is 69.7 %. It can be inferred that Team Effectiveness affect Organizational Outcomes of the Academic Staff in the Private Colleges.

Keywords: Team climate, interpersonal relationships, team communication, team composition, interact with wider organization, organization commitment, organization learning, organization performance and organization development.

1. INTRODUCTION

This research attempts to analyze and identify the perceived impact of team work on an organizational productivity by presented of some private educational institutes/colleges in Sultanate of Oman. University academic staff do complex work in an increasingly demanding environment. Traditionally, universities have defined the role of academic staff according to three domains of teaching, research, and service, with primary emphasis placed upon the teaching and research aspects and secondary emphasis upon service or administration.

One of our major sources of wellbeing is our relationship with our family, friends, colleagues, and tutors. Within each of these relationships we have different expectations and different roles. Knowing how to work effectively within these different groupings is therefore an important inter-personal skill we need to develop and continue developing throughout our lives. Working with groups of people at university can be quite varied and understanding how we and others function in these groups can save us a lot of hassle later. This research will be focus on the academic staff working in teams and how that will affect their organization productivity in positive side. So here we have studied teamwork in different private colleges in Oman and there is survey will be taken from each college and the focus on the important point which led to increase the productivity of organization and we can identify the element that affect the productivity of an organization. Let we take first defining teamwork: We should differentiate team and group work. Team is groups of employees who have at least some collective tasks and where the team members are authorized to regulate mutually the execution of these collective tasks and group work defined by a common task requiring interdependent work and successive or integrative action. The challenge for companies nowadays is to deliver quickly and flexibly new quality products and services, to be able to respond to greater and changing demands from clients. Standardization and specialization characterize traditional work organization. The work is divided into different segments, from operation to support roles, in which workers specialize to maximize productivity. Specialization, control, and routine are suitable when a constant demand for standardized products applies. A high-performance workplace focuses on increasing peoples influence on the business as well as the impact of processes, methods, the physical environment, and the technology and tolls that enhance their work. The work performance of the team is higher than individual performance when the work requires a broader scope of knowledge, judgment, and opinion. The advantage of teamwork is significant productivity growth in the spheres that require creative solving of different tasks, a high degree of adaptability and operational management. Teamwork also creates an environment that facilitates knowledge and information exchange and so-called knowledge sharing. Other advantages are the ability of new forms of work organization to increase the potential for innovation that may add value to products or services, moving them into less price-sensitive markets. Teamwork could lead to more job autonomy, greater responsibility, and higher job satisfaction

1.1 Problem Statement

The study considers different factors responsible for teamwork-organization relationship through a research question, ‘whether teamwork affect the organization as a whole?’ To unearth the research gap and to find the answer to the research question, the study aims to fulfill the objectives.

1.2 Theoretical Concepts and Framework

Teams and work groups (French, W.L., Bell, C.H., and Vohra, Jr. V. P 108, 2006)⁽¹⁹⁾

Collaborative management of the work team culture is a fundamental emphasis of organization development programs. The reality is that much of the organization’s work is accomplished directly or indirectly through teams; work team culture exerts a significant influence on individual behavior. In large part, the techniques, and the theory for understanding and improving team processes come from the laboratory training movement coupled with research in group dynamics. An appreciation of the importance of the work teas as a determinant of individual behavior has come from cultural anthropology, sociology, organization theory, and social psychology. Although we will use the terms somewhat synonymously, it is important to make a distinction between groups and teams. “A work group is a number of persons, usually reporting to a common superior and having some face-to-face interaction, who have some degree of interdependence in carrying out tasks for the purpose of achieving organizational goals. A team is a form of group but has some characteristics in greater degree than ordinary groups, including a higher commitment to common goals and higher degree of interdependency and interaction. Jon Katzenbach and Douglas Smith define team as follows: “A team is a small number of people with complementary skills who are committed to a common purpose, set of performance goals, and approach for which they hold themselves mutually accountable. This distinction is particularly relevant in conceptualizing the kinds of teams desired in organization development efforts, in the creation of self-managed teams, and in the development of high-performance teams, including cross-functional teams.

Cross-Functional Teams (French, W.L., Bell, C.H., and Vohra, Jr. V. P 109, 2006)⁽¹⁹⁾

Even though a high proportion of OD team interventions involve working with what we call “intact work teams” (or “formal work groups”, or “natural teams”), OD interventions are also applicable to other team configurations. Cross-

functional (or multi-functional) teams are widely used in organizations, and OD approaches have great utility in the formation and ongoing functioning of these teams. Cross-functional teams might be permanent, but temporary teams can be created to solve ongoing challenges requiring inputs from a member of functional areas. Such cross-functional teams might be permanent, but temporary teams can be created to solve short term problems. Temporary teams might tackle problems such as planning a products changeover or solving a key customer problem. Large companies such as Motorola, Ford, 3M, and General Electric, as well as many small and medium-sized organizations, have used cross-functional teams. As a specific example, in the development of the Saturn automobile at General Motors, cross-functional teams were used from the outset. Rather than have one functional team (say, design) do its work and then “throw the plans over the wall” to the next functional team (say, production), cross-functional teams provide oversight throughout the entire project. In this book,

Thriving on Chaos, Tom Peters advocates increasing the use of cross-functional teams as a means for U.S industry to compete successfully in today’s fast-paced environment.

Effective Teams (French, W.L., Bell, C.H., and Vohra, Jr.V. P 109, 2006)⁽¹⁹⁾

Early writers who directed attention to the importance of team functioning included Rensis Likert and Douglas McGregor, Likert, for example, suggested that organizations are best conceptualized by systems of interlocking groups connected by linking pins-individuals who occupy membership in two groups by being a boss in one group and a subordinate in another. Through these interlocking groups the work of the organization gets done. The key reality seems to be that individuals in organizations function not so much as individuals alone but as members of groups or teams. For an individual to function effectively, frequently a prerequisite is that the team must function effectively.

High-Performance Teams (French, W.L., Bell, C.H., and Vohra, Jr.V. P 110, 2006)⁽¹⁹⁾

High-performance teams have the same characteristics but to a higher degree. Katzenbach and Smith say that strong personal commitment to each other- commitment to the other’s growth and success-distinguishes high-performance teams from effective teams. Team interventions in OD tend to be congruent with the characteristics identified in the preceding lists and are designed to bring about these conditions. Parenthetically, when groups are asked to describe what their groups would be like if they were operating at a highly effective level, they generate lists like the preceding lists. Again, team and work groups are considered to be the fundamental units of organizations as well as key leverage points for improving the functioning of the organization.

Productivity :(reference for business2015)⁽²²⁾

Productivity is an overall measure of the ability to produce a good or service. More specifically, productivity is the measure of how specified resources are managed to accomplish timely objectives as stated in terms of quantity and quality. Productivity may also be defined as an index that measures output (goods and services) relative to the input (labor, materials, energy, etc., used to produce the output).

1.3 Literature Review

Impact of Team Work on Organizational Outcomes.

There are a lot of literature review on teamwork, productivity of an organizations and teamwork & productivity. I have collected the following literatures:

Tohaidi, H. (2011) ⁽¹⁾ In this research which have been taken from (Islamic Azad University, South Tehran Branch, Tehran, Iran). Tohaidi found that activities in an organization require a lot of interaction and communication between the people involved. Additionally, good activity often relies upon the ability of cross functional team to create a shared understanding of the task, the process, and the respective roles of its members. To effectively operate with teams, organization must know to make, use, and keep them and their members. This paper provides a survey of research on teamwork productivity and effectiveness base on rewards, leadership, training, goals,

wage, size, motivation, measurement, and information technology. The outcome of this study is: it has been observed that (1) the factors that influence the effectiveness of teams at work in organizations. (2) It provides some of the strongest

support for the value of teams to organizational effectiveness. Their motivation was to identify how team works can be used effectively in an organization. Ideally, this foundation will assist researchers currently engaged in teamwork productivity and effectiveness and may lead to the identification and stimulation of areas requiring additional research

Tarricone, P. and Luca, J. (2002) ⁽²⁾ In this research have seen they were focused on final year students enrolled in the Interactive Multimedia course at Edith Cowan University which whom they were required to develop skills and expertise in managing the design and development of client web sites. They have used teams of

four or five students to utilize their specialist skills to meet a “real need” for an industry client. Team roles include programmers, graphic designers, and project managers. There were 82 students (20 teams) completing this unit. The aim was to have students experience project management issues that occur when dealing with “real” clients in “real” projects and was heavily focused on teamwork and problem solving. In this paper they were identifies a range of attributes considered necessary for successful teamwork. They are comparing two contrasting team. The results from this study indicate that these key attributes need to be carefully considered by both tutors & students when teamwork activities are proposed.

Manzoor, S.R., Ullah, H., Hussain, M. and Ahmed, Z.M. (2011) ⁽³⁾ This research study analyze the effect of teamwork on employee performance about the staff members of higher education department (KPK) Peshawar Province of Pakistan. Several measures of employee performance were analyzed including esprit de corps, team trust and recognition and rewards. There is clear evidence that teamwork and other measures of employee performance are positively related with employee performance. The self-administered questionnaires were distributed within the Directorate of Higher Education, (KPK) Peshawar, including four Government Degree Colleges (GDC's) of boys and girls located in Peshawar and Kohat area. The research study uses regression and correlation techniques to analyze the relationship between two variables that is Teamwork and Employee Performance. The result of the study shows that there is a significant positive impact of predictors on the response variable. The study recommends that to adapt teamwork activities to enhance the employee performance. Future research areas have also been indicated in this study... Several measures of employee perform were analyzed including Spirit de corps and Team trust and recognition and rewards.

Syverson, C. (2011) ⁽⁵⁾ The research into the productivity differences across businesses has come a long way since Bartelsman and Doms (2000) surveyed the literature a decade ago. We know more about what causes the measured differences in productivity, and how factors both internal and external to the plant or firm shape the distribution. These insights have been applied to research questions in numerous fields. That said, there is still plenty to be learned. This research done in University of Chicago and National Bureau of Economic Research. There are many people who make this research to be success. Eric Bartelsman, Nick Bloom, Roger Gordon, John Haltiwanger, Chang-Tai Hsieh, Ariel Pakes, Amil Petrin, John Van Reenen, and anonymous referees for helpful comments. This work is supported by the NSF (SES-0519062 and SES-0820307), and both the Stigler Center and the Centel Foundation/Robert P. Reuss Faculty Research Fund at the University of Chicago Booth School of Business.

1.4 Significance of Study

Scope of the Work : (Jane .M 2015) ⁽²³⁾

Teamwork is important in an organization because of the scope of the work it performs daily. A single employee cannot take on all the responsibilities of an organization, according to Net Team. Each employee hired by the company has a certain skill set, which contributes to a single department. In other words, a single department has a collection of workers who each contribute something to reach the organization's goals and objectives. ⁽²³⁾

Physical Distances : (Jane .M 2015) ⁽²³⁾

Some organizations have managers and executives who travel frequently, meaning they are not in the office every day. These individuals communicate via email and telephone to stay updated with tasks, assignments, and production. Teamwork is important in these situations, because modern technology allows all employees to stay in touch about tasks and assignments despite being miles or time zones apart. Teamwork in these situations also shows trust and reliability because employees trust that other workers get the job done in their absence. ⁽²³⁾

Departments and Teamwork :(Jane .M 2015) (23)

Each organization is made up of various departments. Sometimes these departments must work together in creating a project or task for the organization, such as the production department working closely with the accounting department to create products on a budget. These departments must work together as a team to meet the company's goals and objectives, despite having very different functions within the organization.

Ethnicities and Backgrounds :(Jane .M 2015) (23)

Another important reason for teamwork in an organization is the different backgrounds and ethnicities of people working in a single organization. Each employee has a different background or experience, meaning each of them can perform differently on any given tasks. Teamwork is important as these differences get ironed out, so all employees think and perform with the same goal in mind. In addition, all employees understand the methods used to reach these goals.

Work Efficiency :(Gloal post 2015) (24)

Teamwork enables you to accomplish tasks faster and more efficiently than tackling projects individually. Cooperating on various tasks reduces workloads for all employees by enabling them to share responsibilities or ideas. Teamwork also reduces the work pressure on every worker, which allows him to be thorough in the completion of the assigned roles. In sharing ideas or responsibilities, every employee should have a role that suits his specialization. You should also consider employees' levels of interest in the project at hand, which positively influences the efficiency or speed of their output in accomplishing the task.

Improved Employee Relation (Gloal post 2015) (24)

Teamwork is important in an organization because it provides employees with an opportunity to bond with one another, which improves relations among them. Workers who constitute a team working on a project often feel valued upon the successful completion of such tasks. A situation in which all of them find a chance to contribute towards the tasks improves relations within the team and enhances their respect for each other. Improved employee relations also result from the fact that teamwork enhances cohesion among members, thanks to increased trust among them.

Increased Accountability:(Gloal post 2015) (24)

Teamwork increases the accountability of every member of the team, especially when working under people who command a lot of respect within the business. Team members do not want to let each other down and hence do their best to contribute to the successes of their teams. In contrast to working solo on a project, peer pressure is usually high within teams such that cases of low morale are less likely to impact individuals. As a business owner, you would benefit from increased productivity through efficient team projects, which may be completed well ahead of the deadline.

Learning Opportunities :(Gloal post 2015) (24)

Cooperating on a project is an opportunity for new workers to learn from more experienced employees. Teams often consist of members who differ from one another in terms of skills or talents. Working together is a great opportunity to acquire skills that an employee never had beforehand. Unlike working alone on a project, teamwork affords people the opportunity to challenge the ideas of each other and come up with a compromise solution

that contributes to the successful completion of the task.

1.5 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were-

1. To identify the factors that induces teamwork within an organization.
2. To report the phenomena of teamwork.
3. To report the phenomena of organizational outcomes.
4. To identify the relationship between teamwork and organizational outcomes.
5. To observe the impact of team work on organizational outcomes.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The scope of this study is restricted to Muscat region. The emphasis was to identify the factors that affect the productivity of an educational organizations such as colleges, and the most important factor is the teamwork and how it is affect the academic staff to improve the productivity of the private colleges as the following: Arab Open University, Middle East College, Gulf College, Higher College of Technology, Modern College of Business & Sciences, German University of Technology in Oman, and Caledonian College of Engineering. This extent to enable the private colleges to conduct better teamwork for increasing productivity of an organizations.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

The research design is the " blueprint " of study means it is the framework of plan for a study. Descriptive research design was used in this study by applying questionnaire. A structural questionnaire was used to collect. The data in descriptive research is usually accurate, factual, and systematic but it cannot describe the cause and effects about every think of phenomenon. a descriptive research method can provide several answers to various aspects being studied because you have the numerical element as well as the personal and observational element involved.

2.2 Sampling Design

A sample design is the framework, or road map, that serves as the basis for the selection of a survey sample and affects many other important aspects of a survey as well. In a broad context, survey researchers are interested in obtaining some type of information through a survey for some population, or universe, of interest. One must define a sampling frame that represents the population of interest, from which a sample is to be drawn. The sampling frame may be identical to the population, or it may be only part of it and is therefore subject to some under coverage, or it may have an indirect relationship to the population. The sample design provides the basic plan and methodology for selecting the sample. In this study, the sample size were 30 academic staff from each of these college: (Scientific College of Design, Mazoon College, Majan University College, Middle East College, Gulf College, German University of Technology in Oman, and Caledonian College of Engineering) which located all in Muscat.210 questionnaires were distributed. From the filled questionnaires 95 were found complete and valid for the study. The respondents classified into college name, gender, age group, educational level, department, and occupation. The questionnaire attached that each topic has been collected from different sources as its mention in the annexure. The Team Effectiveness Factors elements have been collected from : B. Senior and S. Swaile, P 146, (2010)⁽²⁰⁾ and the Organizational outcomes factors elements has been collected from different sources such as Organization commitment from Schreyer Institute for Teaching Excellence, (2015)⁽²⁵⁾, Organization Learning from Knowledge Networks, (2010)⁽²⁶⁾, Organization Performance from U.S Government Accountability Office (2015) ⁽²⁷⁾ and Organization Development from Agriculture & Life Sciences- Texas A&M University (2015)⁽²⁸⁾ and after taking from the sources some items were deleted which was not require in the study.

2.3 Data Collection Method(s)

Data collection is the process of gathering and measuring information on targeted variables in an established systematic fashion, which then enables one to answer relevant questions and evaluate outcomes. The data collection component of research is common to all fields of study including physical and social sciences, humanities, and business. While methods vary by discipline, the emphasis on ensuring accurate and honest collection remains the same. The goal for all data collection is to capture quality evidence that then translates to rich data analysis and allows the building of a convincing and credible answer to questions that have been posed. In this study the primary data was collected from designed questionnaire. Secondary data was collected from different sources such as article, internet, literature, and books.

2.4 Analysis of Data: Tools & Techniques

Regarding the primary data analysis, the questionnaire was used to analyze the perceived impact of teamwork in an organizational productivity based on the following factors, such as: team climate, interpersonal relationships, team communication, team composition and interact with wider organization. The questionnaire structure is using Likert scale, a statement with which the respondent shows a specific amount of agreement/disagreement. Has five points, select anyone of them it based on the degree important of question to the respondents. A Likert item is simply a statement that the

respondent is asked to evaluate by giving it a quantitative value on any kind of subjective or objective dimension, with level of agreement/disagreement being the dimension most used. Well-designed Likert items exhibit. The format of a typical five-level Likert item, for example, could be:

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

Table 2.4.1. Factors that affect teamwork within an organization

	Determinants		Specific attributes used in questionnaire
1	Team Climate	1	Mutual trust and support
		2	Member's enjoyment
		3	Members look after each other's
		4	Members try not to let each other down
2	Interpersonal relationships	5	Team leader carries his responsibilities
		6	Leadership style used.
		7	Equity of distribution tasks
		8	Gives team members scope to contribute
3	Team Communications	9	Organizational climate support team
		10	Fitting goals of team with goal of an organization
		11	Support team to develop
		12	Team respected by another department
4	Team Composition	13	Teams work to common purpose
		14	Priority of organization objectives
		15	Achieving team goals
		16	Members believe in the objectives
5	Interact with wider organization	17	Roles are clearly defined
		18	Responsibilities are clearly defined
		19	Team members know what is required.

Table 2.4.2. Teamwork and organizational outcomes:

1	Organization Commitment	1	Organization culture and team commitment
		2	Recommendation of team toward organization
		3	Teamwork and success of departments
		4	Team commitment to customer service.
2	Organization Learning	5	Free talking about problems.
		6	Team opinion and consistency with their believe.
		7	Teamwork and completing task.
		8	Team interested in doing things
3	Organization Performance	9	Teamwork and completion task at time
		10	Teamwork and attracting customer
		11	Teamwork and teaching quality
		12	Teamwork and avoiding conflict
4	Organization Developments	13	Team and multi-ideas drawn
		14	Team participation
		15	Team and decision making
		16	Team and strategic planning

Organizational outcomes factors elements has been collected from different sources such as Organization commitment from Schreyer Institute for Teaching Excellence, (2015)⁽²⁵⁾, Organization Learning from Knowledge Networks, (2010)⁽²⁶⁾, Organization Performance from U.S Government Accountability Office (2015) ⁽²⁷⁾ and Organization Development from Agriculture & Life Sciences- Texas A&M University (2015)⁽²⁸⁾ and after taking from the sources some items were deleted which was not require in the study.

Data Analysis:

Data was analyzed using SPSS version 22. The aim was to identify determinants team effectiveness factors that has most impact to organizational outcomes. The questionnaire scales were checked for reliability.

Reliability Analysis:

Reliability of all the five scales of determinants was computed using SPSS software. Cronbach's Alpha and split half reliability coefficient were calculated to establish the reliability of measures. Malhotra ⁽²⁹⁾ indicated limit of 0.6 for acceptable reliability in terms of internal consistency, hence Cronbach's Alpha value of more than 0.6 was considered good for reliability of the measures. All the five scales had Cronbach Alpha greater than 0.6 showing that the scales were reliable.

2.5 Limitations to the Study

1. Less of secondary information from the websites of the organizations.
2. Lack of researcher knowledge in using modern statistical calculation software
3. Respondents have not answered all question in the questionnaire.
4. Very limited duration of study (4 months).
5. The time of getting academic staff to be free is difficult challenge
6. Each Private college has its own roles to accept the people for outside who make their questionnaire within their colleges.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Findings of the Study

According to nine (9) factors we are using in this research, we have applied these factors into seven private colleges in Muscat then we can compare the result for each college. This part shows data that I found by using statistics explain by the schedule that help by the First: Check the reliability of all five scales of both team and outcomes of an organization, second: Finding the Regression and Finally also finding the correlation.

3.2 Discussion on findings of the study

Reliability:

Table 3.2.1: Reliability Analysis of Team Effectiveness variables:

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.959	.959	19

Table 3.2.2: Reliability Analysis of Organizational Outcomes variables:

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.955	.955	16

The reliability coefficient value was found bit highly significant (0.959) for Team Effectiveness that depicted high item reliability. Similarly, the Organizational Outcomes reliability coefficient value was (0.955) and depicted high reliability. Reliability test was applied using SPSS.

Frequency:

Part 1 (Frequency of Demographic Profile)

These tables showing the frequency of demographic profile of the respondents according to the college name, gender, age group, education level, department, and occupation each on separately in its frequency table.

Frequency according to college name

The highest frequency here is coming to the Scientific College of Design which we have got 23 respondents from them up to 95 respondents. That means 13.7 % is the highest percentage of respondent form the Scientific college of Design.

Table 3.2.3: Frequency according to college name

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Middle East college	13	13.7
Gulf College	11	11.6
Caledonian College of Engineering	12	12.6
German University	11	11.6
Scientific College of Design	23	24.2
Mazoon College	13	13.7
Majan College	12	12.6
Total	95	100.0

Frequency according to the gender

as the following table we can see male respondent was higher than female, which the percentage of males were 60% and the females were 40%.

Table 3.2.4: Frequency according to gender

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Male	57	60.0
Female	38	40.0
Total	95	100.0

Frequency according to the age group:

The most academic staff have answered the questionnaire, they were between 30-40 age group which is showing in this table, the percentage is 46% and the least percentage is going to above 50 which the percentage is 7%

Table 3.2.5: Frequency according to the age group:

	Frequency	Percent
Valid 20-30	16	16.8
30-40	46	48.4
40-50	26	27.4
above	7	7.4
Total	95	100.0

Frequency according to educational level of respondent:

The academic staff who have master's degree were the highest frequency respondent, they have got 51.6 % and who have diploma were the least percent of frequency got 12.6 %.

Table 3.2.6: Frequency according to educational level of respondent:

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Diploma	12	12.6
	Bachelor	21	22.1
	Master	49	51.6
	PhD	13	13.7
	Total	95	100.0

Frequency according to the Occupation

According to the Occupation of the respondent, as showing in this table 47.4% of respondents were Lecturer

Table 3.2.7: Frequency according to the Occupation

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Lecturer	45	47.4
	Lab Instructor	24	24.2
	Other	27	28.4
	Total	95	100.0

Frequency according to the department:

Here IT department are most academic staff who were able and ready to fill the questionnaire and they were most people who were interest with the research topic, it people respondent frequency is 66.3 % as given in the table.

Table 3.2.8: Frequency according to the department:

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	IT	63	66.3
	Math	10	10.5
	English	15	15.8
	Electronic Engineering	4	4.2
	Digital Communication	3	3.2
	Total	95	100.0

Descriptive statistics of independent variables (Team Effectiveness)

In the descriptive statistics of team effectiveness factors we have taken the average of each factor separately then we have found the mean and standard deviation of each average factors, so in this table we have got the highest mean for the (Average of team communication factor = 3.7737) and the highest standard deviation is for the (Average of interact with wider organization factor = .974). From the given the arithmetic mean values ranging (3.51 to 3.77), the Average of team climate factor was very less effect on the organizational outcomes whether the mean of communication factor was highly affecting the outcomes of an organization.

Table 3.2.9: Descriptive statistics of independent variables (Team Effectiveness)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Average of Team Climate Factor	95	1.00	5.00	3.5105
Average of Interpersonal Relationships Factor	95	1.00	5.00	3.7500
Average of Team Communication Factor	95	1.00	5.00	3.7737
Average of Team Composition Factor	95	1.00	5.00	3.7553
Average of Interact with wider organization Factor	95	1	5	3.75
Average of Team Effectiveness	95	1.00	5.00	3.7088
Valid N (listwise)	95			

Descriptive statistics of dependent variables (Organizational Outcomes)

In the descriptive statistics of Organizational Outcomes factors, we have taken the average of each factor separately then we have found the mean and standard deviation of each average factors, so in this table we have got the highest mean for the (Average of Organization development factor = 3.8842) and the highest standard deviation is for the (Average of Organization Learning factor= .89198). From given the arithmetic mean values ranging

(3.71 to 3.88). In the view of the arithmetic mean of each element in questionnaire of Organizational outcomes, we found that highly dependent variables were organization developments 3.88 where the lowest mean was for organization learning 3.71

Table 3.2.10: Descriptive statistics of dependent variables (Organizational Outcomes)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Average of Organization commitment Factor	95	1.00	5.00	3.7211
Average of Organization Learning Factor	95	1.00	5.00	3.7105
Average of Organization Performance Factor	95	1.00	5.00	3.7711
Average of Organization Development	95	1.00	5.00	3.8842
Average Organizational Outcomes	95	1.00	5.00	3.7717
Valid N (listwise)	95			

Correlation:Test the team effectiveness and outcomes using correlation

The correlation coefficient (Person) between Team Effectiveness

and Organizational outcomes for members of the study sample of (.840) with significance level (0.00). This indicates that the Team Effectiveness and Perceived Organizational Outcomes is slightly significant because the significance value is reported as 0.000 which is nearly 0.05.

Table 3.2.11: Test the team effectiveness and outcomes using correlation

		Correlations	
		Average of Team Effectiveness	Average Organizational Outcomes
Average of Team Effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	1	.840**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	95	95
Average Organizational Outcomes	Pearson Correlation	.840**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	95	95

Regression:

Multiple regression of Teamwork Effectiveness with Organizational

Outcomes Factors:

Table 3.2.12: Test the team effectiveness and outcomes using Regression

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.845 ^a	.713	.697	.42420

Table 3.2.13: The significance value of relationship between Team Effectiveness and Organizational Outcomes.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	39.843	5	7.969	44.283	.000 ^b
	Residual	16.015	89	.180		
	Total	55.858	94			

The model summary table shows that the multiple correlation coefficient R using all the predictors simultaneously is .845 (R square= 0.713) and the adjusted R square is 0.697 meaning that 69.7 % of the variance of Organizational outcomes affecting by Team Effectiveness.

Based on the result it can be inferred that Team Effectiveness is significantly impacting Organizational outcomes because the variance explained is 69.7 %. It can be inferred that Team Effectiveness affect Organizational Outcomes of the Academic Staff in the Private Colleges. The relationship was also found significant because the significance value was reported as 0.000, which is small compared to 0.05 level.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that the five independent variables which I have chosen to make my research : Team climate, interpersonal relationships, team communication, team composition and interact with wider organization was affect strongly the organizational outcomes such as :Organization : commitment, learning, performance and development as my research which was focused on the private colleges in Muscat and this research focused the academic staff .As my found , the most academic staff are prefer to work in teams and they believe that working in team are better than working individually to enhance an image of an organizational as a whole and that will lead to more than what the team expected from their effectiveness. In the Educational area they need to implement working in team in so many tasks because of high numbers of teaching faculties in each college and because of huge numbers of students there so working in teams that will help the academic staff to handle the teaching part and the activities event to be completed successfully. The academic staff are showing their ability to work in team to enhance their college reputation to achieve their organizational goal. The reliability coefficient value was found bit highly significant (0.959) for Team Effectiveness that depicted high item reliability. Similarly, the Organizational Outcomes reliability coefficient value was (0.955) and depicted high reliability. As the result from arithmetic mean values ranging (3.51 to 3.77), the Average of team climate factor was very less effect on the organizational outcomes whether the mean of communication factor was highly affecting the outcomes of an organization. And the highly dependent variables were organization developments 3.88 where the lowest mean was for organization learning 3.71. According to correlation test it was indicating that the Team Effectiveness and Perceived Organizational Outcomes is slightly significant. Based on the result of regression test it can be inferred that Team Effectiveness is significantly impacting Organizational outcomes because the variance explained is 69.7 %. It can be inferred that Team Effectiveness affect Organizational Outcomes of the Academic Staff in the Private Colleges. The relationship was also found significant because the significance value was reported as 0.000, which is small compared to 0.05 level.

In the end it was observed that Team Effectiveness is affected on the organizational outcomes and it's more related to the teamwork than another dimension. So, in this research it is showing the high positive result of working in teams among academic staff within their organization and the organization also should focus on team work to enhance its productivity and outcomes from this effective factor.

5. SUGGESTIONS & DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

5.1 Suggestions

My research was in "Impact of team work on organizational outcomes", The case study was "Scientific college of Design, Mazoon college, Majan College, Caledonian college, University of German, Middle east college and Gulf college"

1. Lack of doing workshop about important of teamwork within an organization. This needs some motivation from the top management
2. Creating more activities and events which require the team work to complete the event successfully.
3. Assigning rewards to the best department who's implement the teamwork within their department in every year or from time to time.
4. The organization should focus on employee who like to work as leader and can handle the department, because they can lead to be a leader of the team.
5. As we can see from the result, the IT group are more interest to work in team, may because of practical task they are doing but the organization should focus on the admission department to work in team also.

6. In this research we have taken 5 independent variables such as: team climate, interpersonal relationships, team communication, team composition and interact with wider organization. And the dependent variables as the following: Organization: commitment, learning, performance, and development but the outcome of teamwork is not only these. there are unlimited positive outcomes from the teamwork.

7. Teamwork effectiveness is not only good for organizational outcomes. if you have research on other topic as “impact of team work on the marketing” may this will lead to increase in profitability of firms.

5.2 Directions for Future Research

In my research of impact of team work on organizational outcomes. The result and finding of this research are in positive way and let i point some suggestions for future research:

- 1) The main goal of this research is to motivate an academic staff within private colleges to work in team
- 2) Working in teams can be implement in different way and there is no role to follow, so that will be free in discussion between the employees who want to create team and then discuss with the top management or head of department they belong to.
- 3) The objective of this research is to find the factors that affect the teamwork within private colleges.
- 4) The studying of teamwork should have relationship between team effectiveness and organizational outcomes as whole.
- 5) The aim of this study also is to identify the outcomes which we can get through teamwork and how will lead to successful of an organization in the educational area.
- 6) This research focused on the academic staff but if it is implemented by using sample of students from each college that also will show different view of this kind of study because teamwork among students will associate with their studying area not in teaching.

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